

FLUI

PERCEIVING TIME AND SPACE THROUGH EMOTION

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ABSTRACT

Rui Barbosa square, located in the center of Curitiba, Paraná, Brazil, was defined as the focus of our project since it is mainly used as a passage area. Since it is a vast space with substantial crowd circulation and in need of revitalization, we saw the opportunity to design an object that awakes curiosity and self-consciousness among people that pass through this square. Flui is a modular installation that focuses on the interaction between the users and the surroundings in an ephemeral way, providing a brief moment of relaxation and the sense of belonging to the city. The result is a dynamic product that stimulates the connection of people with their surroundings. Furthermore, it aesthetically contributes to the square presentation, attracting the attention of those who do not value the fusion between the urban space and its citizens.

KEYWORDS: *product design, emotional design, installation*

OBJECTIVES

Urban installations have been progressively more exploited worldwide. Studies concerning aridity and tension of modern cities and their influence on human quality of life have increased. In this scenario, the Flui project concept was developed. Due to a tight routine, people travel in a hurry through the city, without contemplating their surroundings, without realizing their actions, establishing sameness and stress in their day-to-day lives. According to Giroto, "The human being has the right and the need to leisure and to a daily relief" (Giroto, 2009, p.15). This quotation expresses the essence of the project: to cause a transient smile during the use of the installation, an action with an ephemeral effect, that functions as a punctual improvement in the user's stressful routine, breaking it and allowing the user to modify and interact with the public space.

Jaime Lerner, an important Brazilian architect and urbanist, coined the term "urban acupuncture" to define simple and punctual actions that result in improvements to the city and its citizens (Urban Acupuncture, 2003). In this project, we intend to do a brief "acupuncture", making the passersby's day more interesting and contributing to the public space. We

also intend to awake a provocation in the bystanders, to allow them to enjoy a moment of real consciousness, depicted in the exact instant they stamp their footprints and realize how their actions can impact the physical space and the society.

The perception is provided by a brief interaction between the user and the product, an installation placed on the floor, without the need to increase the permanence period in the square since the interaction occurs along the route.

Figure 1. Project concept (source: the authors)

PROJECT LOCATION

Once again, Giroto (2009) incites a relevant issue for the project - the rescue of the original function of squares. It is believed that inserting a new element in space can arouse the curiosity in the passerby, which can contribute to rescue the squares' purpose "The squares, being places that receive many bystanders daily, and are available for the enjoyment of all, should be more valued and have their original purposes rescued, becoming a mean of physical and psychological relief for the city and its people" (Giroto, 2009, p.7).

Thus, as a case study, a large downtown square in Curitiba, Brazil, was selected - Rui Barbosa Square. It once hosted major events and circuses, but today it is perceived as a bus terminal in the open. This square holds ideal characteristics for a case study: it houses 44 bus lines, resulting in a large flow of people walking in a short period of time, a factor that demands quick interactions and increases the visibility of the project.

Due to the large amount of people circulating, especially at peak times, it was necessary to perform a flow analysis to understand the dynamics of the square and establish a strategic location for the project application.

The mapping was done by an observational method: on different days and hours we visited the square and observed, annotated and photographed the crowd, identified its habits and sketched its flows. We also observed the square from the top, on the terrace of a nearby building. This procedure allowed us to obtain information required to understand the flow paths and densities and how flows were distributed (red lines

Figure 2. Rui Barbosa Square (source: internet)

Figure 3. Flow analyses (source: the authors)

Figure 4. Modules specifications (source: the authors)

in figure 3). This corresponds to peak periods in the square: the lunch hour (12:00 to 14:00) and late afternoon (17:00 to 19:00). After the flow analyses, it became evident that the area in front of the largest bus stop has the largest circulation of people and is, therefore, the ideal area for implementation.

Since the project is located in a public space, it is not restricted to a target group, but can be seen by anyone who passes by.

FLUI

Flui project consists of a modular hydrochromic floor installation. The modules are placed on the ground, over the walking area of the bystanders. Each module is covered with a hydro-sensitive ink layer, and has low relief line drawings. Together, they create a colorful pattern.

The modules are classified in three categories: the ones that release water, the ones that carry water, and the ones that disperse water. The water runs through the indents until it reaches the disperse modules, which is where the interaction happens. All modules are sensitive to water and the users can interact with the entire installation.

The Modules

Each module measures 70,0 x 70,0 x 3,0 cm. The low reliefs are 1,5 cm deep and act as communicating vessels, allowing the water to flow through the installation.

Figure 5. Releasing module and dispersing module (source: the authors)

Figure 6. Flui's colors (source: the authors)

The releasing water module has a different height – 8 cm instead of 3 cm – and a curved profile (figure 5). This configuration allows water to run more easily.

The disperse water module has an irregular relief to spread the water over the surface (figure 5). The amount of water is enough to moisten the shoe soles of passersby without causing discomfort.

Patterns and Colors

The product was developed in modules in order to solve production issues, such as maintenance and installation.

The different drawings in each module, enable various compositions so that different patterns can be created.

The colors selected and the organic drawings aim to transmit the sensation of calmness and render the surroundings less chaotic.

MATERIALS AND PROCESSES

PVC and Injection

The most appropriate material for the production of the modules is PVC (Polyvinyl Chloride).

According to the PVC Institute (2013), this polymer is resistant to fungi, bacteria, insects, rodents and most chemicals. It is also weatherproof (sun, rain, wind) and durable, making it ideal for outdoors environments.

The process selected was injection molding and five molds were used, one for each module. Since it is possible to add pigments to the resin during the process, each piece can have a specific color.

Hydrochromic Pigment

Hydrochromic ink changes color when it gets in touch with water.

The design consists of two layers of ink on top of each other. When water is applied, the top layer clears, revealing the color underneath. Few drops of water are enough to initiate the reaction. When the water dries (approximately 5 minutes), the original color of the ink is restored.

The hydrochromic pigment is a material that permits the color to appear when the surface is sensitized by water, and it must be applied superficially in all modules. This pigment is indispensable for the effective functioning of the project.

Tests were performed on a functional model to prove the efficiency of the pigment, and the results were positive. After several attempts, the ink layer remained identical to the initial piece.

How Does Flui Interact with the Bystanders?

The default modules are black (not sensitized), meaning no water is in contact with them. Water that is released through the releasing modules each five minutes runs through the in-dents, filling the installation and sensitizing the hydrochromic surfaces. As the black ink fades away, the underneath color is revealed. When the water reaches the disperse modules, it spreads through the installation. Whenever bystanders walk over the water, colorful footprints are left behind. Gradually, as the water dries, the black ink reappears and the footprints fade away.

The purpose of the project is leaving traces, which is a playful way to provoke people to realize the beauty of each moment and that public spaces can and should be places of interaction and expression.

Figure 7. Hydrochromic pigment on functional model (source: the authors)

Figure 8. Product operation (source: the authors)

Figure 9. Simulations use - users interacting with Flui modules (source: the authors)

Flui's purpose is to interact briefly with the bystanders of Rui Barbosa Square, without diverting them from their path or delaying their routines, but stepping in when they are mechanically walking from one point to another.

Daily concerns, duties, stress, are all factors which disconnect people from the surrounding environment and turn the urban context into a tense and arid place.

The idea of Flui is to provide a few seconds of joy for its users, by proposing a brief connection with the city; it is a little surprise that may be capable of awakening the perception of the need to pay attention and be part of the environment.

PROJECT INSIGHT

This project aims to subtly question our busy routine and its impact in our life. It seeks an objective way of contributing to revert this self-destructive process. Furthermore, it enriches the public space, contributing aesthetically to Rui Barbosa's Square, and therefore rescuing one of its original purposes.

The project provokes emotions, stimulating people to discover themselves as citizen that interact with a public place, sharing their sensations and discoveries with strangers and becoming aware of how personal attitudes can affect each other. Thus, a mere place of circulation can acquire a new meaning, turning it into a space that leads users to reflect on questions otherwise not contemplated, such as how they can connect with the environment and the value of citizenship, demonstrating

how a simple use of emotion can generate a complex impact in society's actions.

The potential of this project lies in the fact that people will not have to deviate from their routines. Its functional dynamism, by the appearance and disappearance of footprints, makes Flui always a new experience, not being tiresome and repetitive.

CONCLUSION

The project consists of an idea, a proposal, that was tested in partial prototypes and validated through questionnaires and talks, but it has not been implemented in the square. Indoor tests were realized with mockups and functional models in order to prove the efficiency of the material and perceive people's reactions. The objective, that was to provoke a brief smile and connect people with the environment, was successful since surprise was usually the reaction observed.

As a point of improvement, it is possible to redesign the modules in order to explore different thicknesses in the reliefs, resulting in a better aesthetic appearance.

The main concept of the project is the simplicity of the emotions generated, applied in a fast interaction between the users and the product. The project developed a punctual contribution, which integrates the city and the citizen, valuing the urban space and raising awareness on the impact of the inhabitants on the city.

Although the study was conducted at Rui Barbosa Square, the concept can be adopted in similar places around the globe in order to revitalize the environment and people.

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